

Study of Complications during Pseudo Exfoliation Cataract Surgery in North Karnataka Population

Abhishek Kulkarni¹, Sana Nizami², Sangeeta Patil³, Afreen⁴, Shilpa⁵

¹Associate Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Khaja Banda Nawaz Medical College, Rauza I Buzurg Kalaburgi-585104, Karnataka

²Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Khaja Banda Nawaz Medical College, Rauza I Buzurg Kalaburgi-585104, Karnataka

³Associate Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Khaja Banda Nawaz Medical College, Rauza I Buzurg Kalaburgi-585104, Karnataka

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Khaja Banda Nawaz Medical College, Rauza I Buzurg Kalaburgi-585104, Karnataka

⁵Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Khaja Banda Nawaz Medical College, Rauza I Buzurg Kalaburgi-585104, Karnataka

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sana Nizami

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Pseudoexfoliation (PEX) is an age-related fibrilopathy characterized by the deposition of fibrillar material in the eye with increased risk of complications during cataract surgery.

Method: 90 (ninety) patients above fifty years of age with PEX were studied; planned manual small incision cataract surgery with rigid posterior chamber intraocular lens implantation under peribulbar anesthesia was carried out.

Results: 40 (44.4%) patients had intraoperative complications. The major postoperative complications were 29 (32.2%) corneal edema with SKS, 27 (30%) severe AC reactions, and 13 (14.4%) iris pigment dispersion.

Conclusion: It is concluded that proper preoperative evaluation and modification of surgical technique are essential to manage intraoperative complications and successful cataract surgery with PEX.

Keywords: pseudoexfoliation, visual acuity, intraocular pressure, Slit lamp examination, glaucoma.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Pseudo exfoliation, first described by Lindberg in 1917. It is an age-related, genetically inherited fibrilopathy characterized by gradual synthesis, accumulation, and deposition of abnormal fibrillar extracellular material involving the anterior segment of the eye and other organs [1] Prevalence of pseudoexfoliation (PEX) is 3.8 to 4% in the South Indian population, and 6.45% is reported in China and Pakistan [2]. Major risks of complications during cataract surgery, such as posterior capsular rupture, zonal dialysis, and hyphema, are reported. Intraoperative complications are 4-5 times greater as compared to normal eyes [3]. Most of the complications are mainly believed to be caused by surgical trauma resulting from iris vessel pathology and insufficiently dilated pupils. The immediate postoperative period complications included corneal epithelial and stromal edema, which is more frequent than in normal cataracts. Increased intraocular pressure (IOP), secondary glaucoma, decentration of intraocular lenses (IOL), and other complications and later operative complications were

progressive weakness of the zonules decentration and dislocation of IOL and decomposition of corneal endothelium [4]. Hence an attempt is made to evaluate the complications during pseudoexfoliation (PEX) cataract surgeries.

Material and Method

90 (ninety) elderly patients aged between 50-90 regularly visited the ophthalmology department, Khaja Banda Nawaz Medical College, Rauza I Buzurg Kalaburgi-585104, Karnataka, were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients above 50 years, diagnosed as having cataracts with pseudoexfoliation on the basis of slit lamp examination. The patient gave consent in writing for studies and was selected for study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients below fifty years, patients with traumatic cataracts, congenial cataracts, patients with raised intraocular pressure (> 20 mm of Hg), patients with uncontrolled diabetes

mellitus, and severe cardiovascular diseases were excluded from the study.

Method:

Every patient underwent a detailed medical and ocular history. Visual acuity, papillary dilatation, fundoscopy, lacrimal sac syringing, and intraocular pressure were studied.

A slit lamp examination was done to note the status of the cornea, anterior chamber depth and pigment dispersion, pseudoexfoliation material over the anterior lens capsule and papillary border, and phacodonesis.

Nuclear sclerosis grading and cataract grading were based on the lens opacity classification system (LOCS-III). Intraocular lens power calculation was done using the SRK-T formula.

All the patients were planned for manual small incision cataract surgery with rigid posterior chamber intraocular lens implantation under peribulbar anesthesia. (1) Usage of intraoperative adrenaline (Epitrate), (2) mechanical stretching of the pupil,

(3) sphinctrotomy, (4) type of capsulotomy, and (5) use of CTR/any other untoward event.

Adequate peribulbar block was given, the size of the scleral tunnel corresponding to nuclear sclerosis was fashioned, liberal use of viscoelastic protecting the corneal endothelium was made wherever required, epitrate was used, and sphincterotomy was done, especially in small pupils or nuclear sclerosis > grade 4.

A thorough cortical wash was done, and postoperative topical and systemic steroids or antiglucoma drugs were given appropriately.

Postoperative complications were recorded, and patients were followed up on 1st, 7th, 40th days.

The duration of the study was September 2023 to October 2024.

Statistical analysis: Distribution of age of patients preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative complications were classified with percentage. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software. The ratio of male and female was 2:1.

Figure 1: Site lamp of photograph showing signs of cataract and Pseudoexfoliation

Figure 2: Intraoperative photograph showing capsule retractors stenting the capsular bag during phacoemulsification

Figure 3: Slit lamp photograph showing anterior capsule opacification and phimosis after cataract surgery with in the bag IOL implantation

Observation and Results

Table 1: Distribution of age in pseudo exfoliation patients: 63 (70%) were aged between 50-69, 26 (28%) were aged between 70-89 years, 1 (1.1%) was above 90 years.

Table 2: Pre-operative feature in patients with pseudo exfoliation patients: 24 (26.6%) had a small pupil (< 7mm), 2 (2.2%) had posterior synechie.

Table 3: Study of intra-operative complications in patients with exfoliations: 2 (2.2%) zonal dialysis,

8 (8.8%) difficulty in nucleus delivery, 8 (8.8%) specterotomy, 6 (6.6%) PC rent, 4 (4.4%) iridodiolysis, 4 (4.4%) vitreous loss, 2 (2.2%) hyphaema, and 6 (6.6%) residual cortical matter.

Table 4: Study of post-operative complications: 2 (2.2%) posterior synechiae, 13 (14.4%) iris pigment dispersion, 29 (32.2%) corneal oedema with SKS, 27 (30%) severe AC reaction, 5 (5.5%) post-operative rise of IOP, 7 (7.7%) irregular pupil due to sphincteromy, 6 (6.6%) exudative, 1 (1.1%) de-centred IOL.

Table 1: Distribution of age in pseudo exfoliation patients (Total No. of patients: 90)

Age in years	No of patients	Percentage (%)
50-69	63	70
70-89	26	28
>90	1	1.1
Total	90	100

Figure 4: Distribution of age in pseudo exfoliation patients

Table 2: Pre-operative features in patients with pseudo exfoliation patients

Sl. No	Pre-operative complications	No of patients	Percentage (%)
1	Small pupil (< 7mm)	24	26.6
2	Posterior synechie	2	2.2

Figure 5: Pre-operative features in patients with pseudo exfoliation patients

Table 3: Study of Intra-operative complications in patients with exfoliation

Sl. No	Intra operative complications	No of patients	Percentage (%)
1	Zonal Dialysis	2	2.2
2	Difficulty in Nucleus delivery	8	8.8
3	Sphcterotomy	8	8.8
4	PC rent	6	6.6
5	Iridodialysis	4	4.4
6	Vitreous loss	4	4.4
7	Hyphaema	2	2.2
8	Residual cortical matter	6	6.6
	Total	40	44.4

Figure 6: Study of Intra-operative complications in patients with exfoliation

Table 4: Study of Post-operative complications in patients with pseudo exfoliation

Sl. No	Post-operative complications	No of patients (90)	Percentage (%)
1	Posterior synechiae	2	2.2
2	Iris pigment dispersion	13	14.4
3	Corneal oedema with SKS	29	32.2
4	Severe AC reaction	27	30
5	Post-operative rise of IOP	5	5.5
6	Irregular pupil due to sphincteromy	7	7.7
7	Exudative	6	6.6
8	Decentred IOL	1	1.1
	Total	90	100

Figure 7: Study of Post-operative complications in patients with pseudo exfoliation

Discussion

The present study of complications during PEX cataract surgery. The preoperative features in patients with PEX were that 24 (26.6%) had a small pupil (<7 mm) and 2 (2.2%) had posterior synechie (Table 2). Intraoperative complications were 40 (44.4) (Table 3).

The major postoperative complications were 29 (32.2%) corneal edema with SKS, 27 (30%) had severe AC reaction, and 13 (14%) had Iris pigment dispersion (Table 4) (Figure 1, 2 and 3). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7]. The association between PEX

and the development of cataract is biologically plausible. Electron microscopic examination of the iris vasculature in eyes with PEX revealed multiple abnormalities, including deposits of pseudoexfoliation material lying adjacent to the vascular endothelial wall, thin vessel basement membrane sometimes even interrupted, extreme reduction of vessel lamina through increased volume of the endothelial cells, and fenestration of the vascular endothelial wall [8]. It is also observed that the rate of aqueous flow through the anterior chamber was lower in eyes affected by PEX than in normal eyes. Moreover, it is confirmed that there is impairment of the blood-aqueous barrier in the eyes of those affected

with PEX at the level of the ciliary body (9). Lens metabolism depends on the aqueous. Alterations in the iris vasculature and blood-aqueous barrier could affect the composition of aqueous and subsequently could affect the lens metabolism, resulting in cataract formation.

PEX is a risk factor for open-angle glaucoma. Glaucoma may confound the association between PEX and cataract. Moreover, the nuclear cataract surgery with PEX was successful after adjusting for open-angle glaucoma. This suggests that PEX may contribute to the development of cataract through a pathway different from that responsible for elevated intraocular pressure or open-angle glaucoma [10]. PEX causes zonal fragility, leading to a higher risk of dropped lens. In addition, eyes with PEX dilate poorly, making surgery technically difficult.

As a result, eyes with PEX have a higher rate of operative complications such as capsular rupture, zonular dehiscence, and vitreous loss. PEX had been shown to increase the incidence of posterior capsular opacification after cataract surgery [11]. It is also observed that PEX may also increase the incidence of cataract and cataract surgery.

Summary and Conclusion

As the cataract surgery in pseudo exfoliation is challenging. The proper evaluation intra-operative complications and modified surgical technique will lead to successful cataract surgery with PEX. The present study demands such clinical trials must be carried out in a large number of patients at hi-tech hospitals where the latest techniques are available to combat any surgical emergencies because exact pathophysiology pseudo exfoliation is still unclear.

Limitation of study:

Owing to tertiary location of research centre, small number of patients and lack of latest techniques, we have limited finding and results.

This research work was approved by Ethical committee of Khaja Banda Nawaz Medical College, Rauza I Buzurg Kalaburgi-585104, and Karnataka

References

1. Ring vold A, Davanger M: Iris neurovascular in eyes with pseudo exfoliation syndrome. R. J. ophthalm. 1981. 65 (2); 138-41.
2. Kuchle M, Vinore SA, Mahlow J: Blood aqueous barrier in pseudo exfoliation syndrome evaluation by immune histochemical albumin. Grafes Arch clin. Exp ophthalm. 1996, 234 (1); 12-18.
3. Kanthan GL, Wang JJ: Use of anti-hypertensive medications and topical beta-blockers and the long-term incidence of cataract and cataract surgery Br. J. ophthalm. 2009, 93 (9); 1210-1214.
4. Ritch R, Schlotzer Schrehardt U: Exfoliation syndrome surv. Ophthalmol. 2001, 45 (4); 265-315.
5. Shafiq I, Sharif-ul-Hasan K: Prevalence of pseudo exfoliation syndrome in a given population Pak. J. ophthalm. 2004, 20; 49-52.
6. Tayler HR: Pseudo exfoliation syndrome is an environmental disease. Trans ophthalmol. Soc. UK 1979, 99; 302-7.
7. Duke Elder S: Disease of the Lense and Vitreous, vol. XI, St. Lows. The CV mosby and company 1969, 47-57.
8. Brooks Anv, Gillies WE: The presentation and prognosis of glaucoma in pseudo exfoliation of lense capsule ophthalmology 1988, 95; 271-6.
9. Baig MA, Niazi MK: Pseudo exfoliation syndrome and secondary cataract Pak. Armed Forces Med. J. 2004, 54; 63-66.
10. Carpel EF: Papillary dilatation in eyes with pseudo exfoliation syndrome Am. J. ophthal. 1988, 105; 692-4.
11. Arvind H, Raju P: Pseudo exfoliation in south India Br. J. ophthal 2003, 87; 1321-3.